

WHITE AND LATINX AMERICAN'S PERCEPTIONS ON CLASHING NARRATIVES
UNDER THE TRUMP ADMINISTRATION

By

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6654527

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton

May 2022

Approved by:

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5/13/2022

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Abstract

The narrative of American dream is based on the notion that if individuals work hard enough nothing can hold them back from becoming wealthy and successful.

Diametrically opposed to the narrative of the American dream is the acknowledgment of systematic racism in the United States against people of color. In this exploratory research, we aim to examine if a clashing narrative approach can be used to understand voting behavior in the 2020 US election. In Study 1, I utilize a survey (n=197) to examine if clashing narratives (the American Dream and Systematic racism) predict above and beyond psychological constructs, such as Right-Wing Authoritarianism (RWA) and Social Dominance Orientation (SDO), voter behaviors in the 2020 election. I found that Systematic Racism served as the strongest predictor for people's political position above and beyond psychological constructs. In Study 2, I examine how Trump's policies of increased policing of immigrants crossing the border influence Latinx and White Americans' endorsement of the two narratives important in predicting voter behavior. Results indicate an interaction effect; when primed with news depicting Latinx immigrants suffering at the border, White people but not Latinx decrease their belief in the American Dream and increased their agreement with narratives of Systematic Racism. I discuss the results in terms of Latinx increased support for Trump in the 2022 election.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Earning an undergraduate degree and completing this thesis would not have been possible without the kindness and help I received from many individuals who have guided me throughout my four years at CSUF. Thank you to my family and friends for their love, support, and encouragement these past years. I would not have been able to achieve my academic and career goals without their constant support.

I would like to express my deep appreciation to my advisor and mentor, Dr. Ella Ben Hagai, for her expert advice, support, and understanding throughout the research process. Thank you for your contributions to multicultural psychology and activism for minority groups around the world. As my teacher and mentor, she has taught me more than I could ever give her credit for here. She has shown me, by her example, what a good scientist (and person) should be.

I am grateful to all the individuals with whom I have had the pleasure to work with throughout the duration of my research thesis. My research would not be here if not for the support and hard work by my fellow lab mates in the IC Lab.

CHAPTER 1

STUDY 1: INTRODUCTION

Research on national identity suggests that different national groups hold a master narrative that helps define the country's ethos (Liu & László, 2007; McAdams, 2008; Rotberg, 2006). In the United States, one of the constitutive stories defining what it means to be an American is the American dream (Kasser & Ryan, 1996; McAdams, 2008). The American dream conceptualizes life in the United States based on the notion that if individuals work hard enough, learn how to play the game, and persevere through obstacles, nothing can hold them back from becoming wealthy and successful (Carlin, 2004; Jost et al., 2003; Jost & Hunyady, 2005). The American dream narrative is rooted in Protestant religious beliefs, specifically the protestant work ethic that suggest that through hard work, people can reach salvation (Levy et al., 2006; Weber & Kalberg, 2013).

The narrative of the American dream in which anybody who works hard can move ahead ignores systematic racism in the United States (Armstrong et al., 2019; Torres et al., 2011). Although America is presented as the land of dreams, members of minority groups ability to move ahead is systematical thwarted. Racism is still prevalent in various sectors such as the educational system (Bobo & Fox, 2003), housing loans (Benjamin, 2019; Kenn, 2001), hiring (McConahay, 1983), health services (Rosenthal & Lobel, 2011), and policing (Alexander, 2011), which prevent people of color from having the same opportunities in the United States. Contemporary racism functions by ignoring the legacy and the current reality of racism in the United States and is called “color-blind

racism” (Neville et al., 2005, Bonilla-Silva, 2006). According to Neville et al., (2013) color-blind racism assumes that everybody regardless of their race has the same access to opportunities for success (Bonilla-Silva, 2006; Neville et al., 2013).

Grounded in a clashing narrative approach to political conflict, the purpose of this research is in two-fold. First, we aim to explore if in the United States clashing narratives framework, that argues that the American dream narrative clashes with the systematic racism narrative, is helpful in predicting people political position. More specifically, we examine the strength of the clashing narrative approach in comparison with other central predictors of political ideology, such as Social Dominance Orientation (Pratto et al., 1994) and Right-Wing Authoritarianism (Altemeyer, 1998). Second, we conduct an experiment to test if exposure to the consequence of Trump’s brutal immigration policies leads to disavow of the American dream and decrease in color-blind racism among White and Latinx people. We examine this question using a sample of White and Latinx participants.

This research makes both applied and theoretical contributions. On an applied level, we aim to identify and empirically test the narratives and ideologies that play an important role in shaping people’s political position. Moreover, Latinx participants are an important population to study because they are increasingly a crucial player in determining which party wins the US election (De la Garza, 2004; Jackson, 2011). In the second part of this research, we explore the impact of hostile rhetoric and policies against Latinx immigrants on Latinx and White participants. This exploration helps explain how the hostile rhetoric’s and policies towards Latinx immigrants, impact Latinx people

political position. The "Latino vote" has become a crucial vote in swinging key states blue (Democrats) or red (Republican) states (Jacobs, 2020; Barreto et al., 2008). The theoretical contribution this research is making is by borrowing from the literature on intergroup conflict and clashing narratives to understand political conflict in the US. Our research makes a novel contribution because national narratives have primarily been studied in relationship to intractable conflict (e.g., the Israeli-Palestinian conflict); we use some of the tools from peace psychology, to understand political conflict in the United States. Bringing together constructs from peace psychology illuminates the relationship between ideological narrative and social identity processes.

Narratives and the United States

Research on cognitive processes shows that people are particularly adapted to think, process, and remember information constructed in a narrative form (Bruner, 1991; Nelson, 1998). Narratives have a temporal dimension and usually depict a protagonist facing a problem, the protagonist may resolve the problem to achieve their goal (McAdams, 2001; McCabe et al., 1991; Ochs & Capps, 1996). The psychological construct of a narrative has been integral in understanding why individuals support the perpetuation of conflict (Bar-Tal & Salomon, 2006; Klar & Baram, 2016; Rouhana & Bar-Tal, 1998). For instance, several studies indicate that the narrative that depicts Jewish Israelis as having a strong connection to the land or as wishing to live in peace but must defend themselves clash with narratives that depict the Palestinian as indigenous to the land but as dispossessed and oppressed due to Israel oppression (Ben Hagai et al., 2013; Ben Hagai et al., 2013). Whereas most research uses qualitative methods to study

narratives, a more recent body of research uses a quantitative methodology to operationalize narratives and study their influence on political conflict (Ben Hagi & Zurbruggen, 2019; Klar & Baram, 2016; Liu & László, 2007). Whereas narratives have often been used to study societies in the global south or the Middle East, the premise of this research is that narrative is also essential to political decision-making in the United States.

At the center of what it means to be an American is the master narrative of the American dream. The narrative of the American dream depicts its protagonists as beginning from a disadvantaged and impoverished point, but through hard work, talent, and wisdom, they can fight obstacles and persevere to success (McAdams, 2006; McAdams, 2008). The narrative focus on hard work is derived from the Protestant work ethic that suggests that through hard work and gaining success, the believer finds signs for their redemption (Furnham, 1984; Levy et al., 2006).

The master narrative of the American dream has not been operationalized in psychological research into a scale, nevertheless, in their work on neoliberal beliefs, Bay-Cheng et al. (2015) and colleagues have operationalized a set of beliefs parallel to the American dream depicted in their Personal Wherewithal belief scale. The Personal Wherewithal subscale includes statements arguing that anybody can get a head if they work hard enough. This subscale is correlated with conservative political position and neoliberal position that frames the government as interfering in people's lives (Beattie et al., 2019; Bay-Cheng et al., 2015).

In a pathbreaking research, Hochschild (2018) argues that the story of the American dream is diametrically opposed to acknowledgement of unequal access of resources for minorities living in the United States. She further argues that disavow of policies of affirmative actions is at the heart of Whites support for Trump in the 2016 election (Hochschild, 2018). The narratives that see the United States as unequal country in which minority groups have been historically and systematically marginalized negate the American dream narrative in which anybody who works hard enough can move ahead. Indeed, diametrically opposed to the narrative of the American dream is the acknowledgment of systematic racism in the United States (Neville et al., 2013). The systematic racism narrative argues that people of color compared to white people have less access to resources and opportunities in the United States (Neville et al., 2013; Block; 2016). In this research we use Neville et al., (2003) operationalization of the systematic racism narrative depicted in their color-blind racism scale. We use this scale because it fits well with our theorization of systematic racism narrative that we believe is at the heart of political struggle in the United States and because it has been found to be reliable and valid (Neville et al., 2003). Items part of this scale assess level of agreement with statements that suggest that White people have more opportunities to get ahead compared to people of color. Previous research using this scale has demonstrated that the individuals who hold liberal views are likely to have a lower score on the color-blind racism scale (Hartmann et al., 2017; Cokley et al., 2010; Behar-Horenstein & Garvan, 2016). Conversely, individuals who are identified as holding more conservative views were more likely to score higher on the color-blind racism scale – indicating that these

individuals reject the notion that systematic racism affects minority group members (Hartmann et al., 2017; Behar-Horenstein & Garvan, 2016).

In the first study, we test the clashing narrative approach in comparison to psychological dispositions that have been established to predict individuals' political position such as Right-Wing Authoritarianism (RWA) and Social Dominance Orientation (SDO). According to the (Duckitt et al., 2002) Dual Process Model of Ideological Disposition and Prejudice, two key ideological beliefs are associated with support for conservative parties. The first is Right-Wing Authoritarianism (RWA) (Altemeyer, 1988). Right Wing Authoritarianism is defined by the proclivity to support authority, a strong disposition to conform to cultural traditions and social conventions, and the endorsement of punishment to those who do not obey social norms or are deemed as dangerous outsiders (Altemeyer & Altemeyer, 1996; Altemeyer, 1988). Personality patterns associated with RWA are low levels of openness to experience and high levels of consciousnesses (Hodson et al., 2009; Sibley & Duckitt, 2009; Dallago et al., 2012). People who score high on RWA tend to think about the world as a dangerous place and are motivated towards gaining social control and security (Duckitt et al., 2002; Van Hiel et al., 2007). As such these individuals seek authoritarian leaders who will sustain tradition and scapegoat "social outsiders" (Christopher & Mull, 2016; Livi et al., 2014). Recent research demonstrated that right wing authoritarianism was a better predictor of support for Trump during the 2016 election (Conway III & McFarland, 2019; Choma & Hanoch, 2017; Womick et al., 2019) A study by Major et al. (2018) found RWA to be a significant predictor in support for Republican candidates, as well as greater group status

threat. These research studies highlight the connection that exists between authoritarianism and election outcomes, but also the predictive power of authoritarianism.

Another ideological belief that explains support for conservative leaders is Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) (Pratto et al., 1994). Social Dominance Orientation is defined by an understanding of the social world as inherently hierarchical with some groups of people being better than others (Pratto et al., 1994; Overbeck et al., 2004). People who are high on SDO justify social inequalities and see them as reflecting a natural and positive aspect of social relations (Levin et al., 2002; Oldmeadow & Fiske, 2007; Overbeck et al., 2004). In terms of personality, people who are high on SDO tend to score lower on Agreeableness part of the Big Five personality trait inventory (Perry & Sibley, 2012; Akrami & Ekehammar, 2006; Pratto et al., 1994). These people tend to understand the social world as a competitive jungle in which the strongest and fittest excel (Duckitt, 2002; Federico et al., 2009). Choma and Hanoch, (2017) found that when controlling for party affiliation, RWA and SDO played significant role in explaining the variance in support for Trump or Hillary in the 2016 election. These results are replicated in other studies that found SDO predicted support for Trump or having previously voted Donald Trump for president (Wright & Esses, 2019; Womick et al., 2019). The results of these studies emphasize the significance SDO, and its constructs have on real world desires of dominating out-group members.

This Research

In this exploratory research we first examine if a clashing narrative approach can be used to understand political positionality in the 2020 US election. Specifically, in

Study 1, we examine if the clashing narrative framework that depicts the American dream as clashing with the systematic racism narrative, predicts above and beyond more traditional measures of political ideology such as RWA and SDO positioning on the conservative liberal continuum. In Study 2, we examine how recent policies of increase policing and the imprisonment of immigrants crossing the borders impact Latinx and White Americans endorsement of the two narratives in the heart of the American ethos: that of the American dream and systematic racism.

CHAPTER 2

METHOD

Participants

Participants for this survey were recruited through online forums such as Reddit subgroups and Facebook survey groups and snowballing methods. Data collection was completed in 2020. The study was described as studying political beliefs regarding issues such as BLM, universal income, privatization, and more. Participants had to be 18 years or older to complete the survey, and no compensation was given to participants who completed the survey.

One hundred and ninety-seven completed all the relevant measures for this study. The youngest participant was 18 and the was oldest 70 ($M = 28.99$, $SD = 10.86$). Of these participants, 80 (40.6%) identified as Men, 106 (53.8%) identified as Women, 9 (4.6%) identify under the transgender umbrella, and two (1%) did not answer the question. In terms of participants race and ethnicity, 76 (38.6%) are White, 61 (31%) are Latinx, 26 (13.2%) are Asian, 7 (3.6%) are Middle Eastern, 4 (2%) are Indian or Alaskan Native, 4 (2%) are Black or African American, and 19 (9.6%) choose Other or did not answer the question. In terms of household income, 66 (33.5%) indicated their income under \$50,000 per year, 66 (33.5%) indicated their income between \$50,000 and \$99,999, and 61 (31%) indicated their income over \$100,000, 4 (2%) did not answer the question. Among participants the highest level of education includes, 25 (12.7%) completed high school or equivalent, 51 (25.9%) had some college but no degree, 37 (18.8%) held an associate degree, 61 (31%) held a bachelor's degree, 19 (9.6%) held a master's degree,

and 4 (2%) held a Ph.D. Finally, in terms of political affiliation, 36 (18.3%) identified their political affiliation as Republican, 128 (65%) as Democrat, 9 (4.6%) as Libertarian, 5 (2.5%) as Green, and 19 (9.7%) as Other or did not answer the question.

Measures

To operationalize the two narratives that we theorize to be at the heart of political conflict in the United States, we choose two scales that were tested to be valid and reliable, the Personal Wherewithal subscale from the Bay-Cheng et al., (2015) Neoliberal Belief Inventory and the Neville (2000) Color-Blind Racism Scale. We examine if these two beliefs (theorize to be part of a central narrative in the United States political debate) contribute to the understanding of political positioning above and beyond other critical dispositions such as RWA and SDO.

Personal Wherewithal.

Personal wherewithal is an 8-item scale measuring the narrative that through hard work anybody can become successful in the United States. This narrative is depicted in the Personal Wherewithal subscale part of the Neoliberal Beliefs Inventory (Bay-Cheng et al., 2015). Items from this sub-scale include, "Anyone can get ahead in the world if they learn to play the game," "When it comes to challenges like discrimination, individuals just have to be tough enough to overcome them," and "A person's success in life is determined more by his or her personal efforts than by society." Participants rated their agreement level on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = *Strongly Disagree*; 7 = *Strongly Agree*). This scale yielded a satisfactory reliability: $\alpha=.95$ (Cronbach's alpha).

Color Blind Racial Attitudes

Color-Blind Racial Attitudes is a 20-item scale that measures the (a) global belief in a just world, (b) sociopolitical dimensions of a just world, (c) racial and gender intolerance, and (d) racial prejudice (Neville et al., 2000). Items from this scale include, "Racism may have been a problem in the past, but it is not an important problem today," "Talking about racial issues causes unnecessary tension," and "Immigrants should try to fit into the culture and adopt the values of the U.S." Participants rated their agreement level on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = *Strongly Disagree*; 7 = *Strongly Agree*). This scale yielded a satisfactory reliability: $\alpha=.96$ (Cronbach's alpha).

Right Wing Authoritarianism

Right-Wing Authoritarianism is a 15-item scale measuring the degree to which people defy established authorities, demonstrate aggression to out-groups, and yield support for traditional values (Zakrisson, 2005). Items from this scale include, "Our country needs a powerful leader in order to destroy the radical and immoral current prevailing in society today," "The "old-fashioned ways" and "old fashioned values" still show the best way to live," and "There are many radical, immoral people trying to ruin things; the society ought to stop them" Participants rated their agreement level on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = *Strongly Disagree*; 7 = *Strongly Agree*). This scale yielded a satisfactory reliability: $\alpha=.81$ (Cronbach's alpha).

Social Dominance Orientation

Social Dominance Orientation is a 9-item scale measuring a person's support for social hierarchy and the extent they find their ingroup to be superior to outgroups (Pratto, 1994). Items from this scale include, "Some groups are simply not the equal of others,"

"Some people are just more worthy than others," and "To get ahead in life, it is sometimes necessary to step on others." Participants rated their agreement level on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = *Strongly Disagree*; 7 = *Strongly Agree*). This scale yielded a satisfactory reliability: $\alpha=.86$ (Cronbach's alpha).

The dependent variable for this study was the 7-point Political Position Likert scale in which 1 represents Extremely liberal, 2 Liberal, 3 Slightly liberal, 4 Moderate Middle of the road, 5 Slightly conservative, 6 Conservative, and 7 Extremely conservative.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS

Data Analysis

IBM SPSS 27.0 was used for all data analyses on this survey research. Descriptive statistics of the dependent variables were tabulated and examined. Correlational analyses were conducted. The Bonferroni correction was applied to maintain an overall Type I error rate of .05 against the multiple comparisons. Both hierarchical regression analyses were applied assuming Political Positionality as the independent variables. Alpha level was set to .05 for all statistical tests.

Correlations

An examination of correlations (see Table 1) revealed that the strongest correlate with political position was acknowledgment of systematic racism as depicted by the Color-Blind Racism scale ($r=.77$) and the American dream depicted by the Personal Wherewithal scale ($r=.70$). RWA was also highly correlated with political position ($r=.66$), and SDO less so ($r=.59$). Importantly, the correlation between the American dream narrative and systematic racism was highly correlated ($r=.81$), indicating the more individuals agreed with statements that depict the American dream as operationalized in the Personal Wherewithal scale, the less they agreed with statement that acknowledge systematic racism in the United States ($r=.81$).

Hierarchical Regression

Prior to conducting a hierarchical multiple regression, the relevant assumptions of this statistical analysis were tested. Firstly, a sample size of 197 was deemed adequate for

four independent variables to be included in the analysis. The singularity assumption was also met as the independent variables (RWA, SDO, Personal Wherewithal, Color-Blind Racism) were not a combination of other independent variables.

We aimed to examine if the narratives we theorized to play an important role in predicting political position would contribute to the variance above and beyond more traditional psychological scales such as RWA and SDO. In the first step, we entered RWA as a predictor of Political Positionality, $F(1, 195) = 1051.07, p < .001, \Delta R^2 = .43$. RWA accounted for 43% of the variance. In the second step we added SDO, adding SDO increased the variance explained by the model by .07, $F(2, 194) = 101.33, p < .001, \Delta R^2 = .51$. In the third step, adding Personal Wherewithal significantly increased the variance explained by the model by .07, $F(3, 193) = 89.35, p < .001, \Delta R^2 = .57$, while SDO lost its significance. In the final step, adding Color Blind Racism increases the variance explained by the model by .07, $F(4, 192) = 90.59, p < .001, \Delta R^2 = .64$, while Personal Wherewithal (see Table 2).

CHAPTER 4

DISCUSSION

Study 1 confirm the important role that RWA and SDO have on predicting political positionality in the United States. It also supports our working hypothesis that master narratives such as the belief in the American dream (depicted by the Personal Wherewithal scale) and Systematic racism (depicted in the Color-blind racism scale) are also at the heart of political debate in the US. Above and beyond more traditional measures of ideological disposition, acknowledgement of systematic racism or disavow of systematic racism through the story that any American who works hard enough can get a head, play a significant role in explaining political position. This narrative has been demonstrated in previous qualitative research on Trump supporters (Hochschild, 2019), as well as qualitative findings which show a strong relationship between beliefs on racism in the US and beliefs in personal wherewithal and political positionality (CITATION).

A clear limitation of this study is that it did not operationalize the two narratives directly but rather used a validates and reliable scales. Our aim was to test an innovate model borrowed from the peace and conflict literature to understand local political debate in the United States. Following this exploratory investigation future research should operationalize these specific narratives and examine if their predictive power greater than the proxy measures, we used in this research.

In the first study, we showed that a Personal Wherewithal Scale that depicts the American dream, and the Color-Blind Racism Scale depicting systematic racism played a significant role in explaining support for conservative ideology in the 2020 election. In

Study 2, we aimed to understand how the escalation of hostile rhetoric and draconian policies against Latinx people and immigrants from Latin American countries during the Trump presidency influenced agreement with the American dream or acknowledgment of systematic racism in the United States, among Latinx and White participants.

CHAPTER 5

STUDY 2: INTRODUCTION

Since his election campaign in 2015-2016, Donald Trump amplified harmful and toxic rhetoric and policies against Latinx people, especially immigrants coming from Latinx countries. For instance, during his campaign for president, Donald Trump accused immigrants from Mexico of being criminals, drug dealers, and rapists (Lee, 2015). The Trump administration pushed for increased funding and staffing for Immigration and Customs Enforcement (ICE) (Emma & Scholtes, 2019). Trump's policies also increased deaths among immigrants who crossed the US-Mexican border (Missing Migrants Project, 2021). Specifically, under the Trump Administration, there were 2,923 reported deaths and missing persons along the US-Mexican border (Missing Migrants Project, 2021). Surprisingly, around the time these policies were enacted, a survey conducted by the Pew Research Center (Lopez et al., 2018) found a high approval rating of how the president was handling his job, with almost 60% approval amongst Hispanic Republicans. The ongoing popularity of Trump among some Latinx voters underlines the importance of understanding the impact of Trump policies, especially in regard to immigration, and their impact on Latinx as well as White voters.

Two theories that can be helpful in explaining and predicting differences in how Latinx compared to White participants may react towards Trump's draconian policies towards immigrants. The Social Identity approach (Tajfel & Turner, 1979; Espinoza & Garza, 1985) predicts that when individuals are categorized into a group they identify with, they are more likely to favor their group over the outgroup. Moreover, social

identity theory argues that when members of an oppressed group come to understand their oppression as escapable through assimilation into the majority group, they may disavow their own group in order of achieving upper mobility studies (Turner et al., 1979; Branscombe & Ellemers, 1998). From this perspective, the narrative of the American Dream in which anybody who works hard can move ahead offers Latinx identified individuals a pathway to avoid the oppression associated with their identity. On the other hand, adopting a systematic color-blind narrative position, position Latinx immigrants as part of a marginalized minority group similar to other marginalized minority groups but with little prospect towards social mobility.

For White identified participants a different model can help explain the impact of being confronted with newspaper reports that depict abuse of immigrants in the border. According to Shnabel and Nadler (2008) Need Based Model of Reconciliation, within an asymmetrical conflict between social groups, such as that between the Israeli and the Palestinians members of the powerful majority groups (Jewish-Israelis) hold different needs than those from the less powerful group (i.e. Palestinians). Members of the more powerful group when confronted by violent or immoral acts will seek to establish their morality in order of reentering the moral community (Shnabel et al., 2009). On the other hand, members of the dispossessed group seek to reestablish their power (Shnabel & Nadler, 2015). From the Need Based Model of Reconciliation, we expect White people to acknowledge the Color-Blind Racism scale and reject the American Dream in order of sustaining the commitment to egalitarian morality.

Based on the results of Study 1, which found the Personal Wherewithal Scale and Color-Blind Scale to play a significant role in explaining support for conservative ideology, we anticipate finding differences in these scales among participants when presented with the impacts of conservative immigration policies imposed by the Trump presidency. Based on the Social Identity Model we predict that Latinx people, when confronted with news articles on immigration oppression and harassment on the borders, will be more likely to believe in PW with narrative of the American dream compared to White participants in the same condition. Based on the Need-Based Model of Reconciliation, we predict White participants will express low support on Institutional Discrimination when confronted with immoral acts against immigrants crossing the border.

CHAPTER 6

METHOD

Participants

The study was described as studying emotions and how it relates to the understanding of modern political policies. Participants had to be 18 years and older to complete the survey, and no compensation was given to participants who completed the survey. Participants for this survey were recruited through online forums such as Reddit subgroups and Facebook survey groups and snowballing methods.

One hundred and forty-seven participants completed this study (M age = 34.40, S = 15.16). Our participants ranged from 18 to 84 years old; however, 56.4% of the participants identified as 30 and under. Of the 147 participants, 58.5% were White, 41.5% were Latinx. Of these participants, 25.2% obtained their high school degree or equivalent, 34.7% obtained their bachelor's degree, 12.2% obtained their master's degree, 25.9% obtained their associate degree, 2% obtained their Ph.D. Of these participants, 19% identified their political affiliation as Republican, 40.1% as Democrat, 17% as Independent, 4.1% as Libertarian, 14.3% as no political affiliation, and 4.1% as other. There was 1.4% unaccounted for as these participants failed to answer their political affiliation. Of these participants, 27.2% identified as male, 70.1% as female, and 1.4% as non-binary, and 1.4% preferred not to say.

Measures

The experiment consisted of several demographic questions, including age, gender, ethnicity, educational attainment, and political affiliation. Color-blind attitudes

were measured with self-reports on three sub-scales from the Color-Blind Racial Attitudes Scale (Neville et al., 2000), including unawareness of racial privilege, institutional discrimination, and blatant racial issues. To operationalize the narratives of the American Dream and acknowledgement of systemic racism in the United States, we chose two scales that were tested to be valid and reliable, the Personal Wherewithal subscale from the Bay-Cheng et al., (2015) Neoliberal Belief Inventory and the Neville (2000) Color-Blind Racism Scale. We examine if these two beliefs help to understand how the escalation of hostile rhetoric against Latinx Americans and immigrants influence our Latinx and White participants.

Personal Wherewithal.

Personal wherewithal is an 8-item scale measuring the belief that personal attributes of strength and skill yield success. Items from this sub-scale include, "Anyone can get ahead in the world if they learn to play the game," "When it comes to challenges like discrimination, individuals just have to be tough enough to overcome them," and "A person's success in life is determined more by his or her personal efforts than by society." Participants rated their agreement level on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = *Strongly Disagree*; 7 = *Strongly Agree*). This scale yielded a satisfactory reliability: $\alpha=.940$ (Cronbach's alpha).

Institutional Discrimination

Institutional Discrimination is a 7-item scale that measures the prejudicial practices and policies within institutions that result in the systematic denial of opportunities (Neville et al., 2000). Items from this scale include, "White people in the

U.S. are discriminated against because of the color their skin," "Immigrants should try to fit into the culture and adopt the values of the U.S.," and "English should be the only official language in the U.S.." Participants rated their agreement level on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = *Strongly Disagree*; 7 = *Strongly Agree*). This scale yielded a satisfactory reliability: $\alpha=.92$ (Cronbach's alpha).

Procedure

This experiment was conducted online through Qualtrics. The study was presented as research on the relationship between emotions and political policies. At the beginning of the study, participants were presented with an empty scale, then they were randomly selected into two different conditions. In the experimental condition they read prompt two stories about women and their children dying at the border (see Appendix A and B). Participants in the control group filled out the survey part of the research without reading any prompt. After answering demographic questions, both conditions were given a debriefing form, in which they were informed some participants read the articles on immigrants' deaths and other participants did not. Participants were thanked for their participation and were given resources for mental health services. Participants generally completed the questionnaire within 15 minutes. The experiment was IRB approved (HSR-19-20-464) and registered on OSF in April 2020 before the commencement of the experiment.

CHAPTER 7

RESULTS

Prior to conducting a two-way analysis, the relevant assumptions of this statistical analysis were tested. A priori power analysis was conducted using G*Power (Faul et al., 2007) to test the effect of two nominal predictor variables on a continuous outcome variable, using a two-tailed test, a medium effect size ($d=.06$), and an alpha of .05. Results showed that a total sample of 154 participants with two equal-sized groups of $n=77$ was required to achieve a power of .80. Outliers were assessed by inspection of a boxplot; normality was assessed using Shapiro-Wilk's normality test for each design cell and Levene's test's homogeneity of variances. There were no outliers, residuals were normally distributed ($p>.05$), and there was homogeneity of variances ($p=.697$).

ANOVA Effects

A two-way ANOVA was conducted to examine the effect of conditions (control vs experimental) and ethnicity (White vs Latinx) on the belief in personal wherewithal. The main effect of conditions was non-significant, $F(1,143) = .070$, $p = .792$, as was the effect of ethnicity, $F(1,143) = .645$, $p = .423$. However, a significant interaction effect was found, $F(1,143) = 4.61$, $p = .033$, $\eta^2 = .031$. The significant interaction effect showcased White participants in the control condition expressed high support ($M = 4.25$, $SD = 1.44$), for Personal Wherewithal whereas Latinx participants in the same condition expressed low support ($M = 3.90$, $SD = 1.58$), for Personal Wherewithal. White participants in the experimental condition expressed low support ($M = 3.76$, $SD = 1.44$), for Personal Wherewithal whereas Latinx participants in the same condition expressed

high support ($M = 4.52$, $SD = 1.64$). When participants were presented with news clips depicting the harassment of immigrants at the border, White participants decreased in their belief of the American dream narrative, whereas Latinx participants increased their belief. Figure 1 presents this result.

We also examined the impact of news clips that depict immigrant harassment at the border on the endorsement of the systematic racism narrative. A two-way ANOVA was conducted to examine the effect of the conditions (control vs experimental) and ethnicity (White vs Latinx) on participant's belief on the Institutional Discrimination scale. A significant main effect on ethnicity was found, $F(1,143) = 5.49$, $p = .021$, $\eta^2 = .037$ in Institutional Discrimination. The main effect on ethnicity demonstrates that when White participants in the experimental condition were confronted with the immoral acts that immigration policies have on immigrants, they decreased their support ($M = 2.93$, $SD = 1.30$), in Institutional Discrimination. Figure 2 presents this result.

CHAPTER 8

DISCUSSION

The results of Study 2 indicate an interaction effect in which White but not Latinx people increased their rejection of statement depicting the American dream after reading about family separation and death at the border. This was not the case for Latinx participants who increased their agreement with statement depicting the American dream compared to Latinx people who were not exposed to news about brutality towards immigrants at the border. This finding can be explained by the Social Identity Theory framework in that when confronted with institutional oppression at the U.S. borders Latinx participants increase their endorsement of the assimilative story of the American dream, in which anybody in America who works hard enough can move ahead. Follow up analysis suggest that White people come to agree with statements that acknowledge institutional racism in the United States, following a prompt depicting death of Latinx immigrants passing the border. In line with Shnabel and Nadler (2008) model, in which members of a more powerful group aim to gain their morality, White participants in our study when being exposed to the brutal treatment of immigrants distanced themselves from the actions of the U.S. government under Trump and agreed to greater extent than White people in the control group, that institutional racism is prevalent in the US. Based on Noor et al. (2012) this is due to White participant aim to sustain their morality in light of the brutal action of the U.S administration towards immigrants.

CHAPTER 9

GENERAL DISCUSSION

The first experiment realized the importance personal wherewithal and color-blind racism have on choosing a political position. We found that both variables were significant in predicting support for more conservative positions. With this information, an experiment was conducted to assess how the effects of the conservative policies of the Trump Administration would then influence White and Latinx participants on their belief in Personal Wherewithal and Color-Blind Racism. The experiment found a significant interaction effect of the conditions and ethnic identity on the belief of Personal Wherewithal. The study also found a significant main effect of ethnic identity on the unawareness of institutional discrimination. Interestingly, our results gave a different impression than our predicted hypothesis, where Latinx participants in the experimental condition did not score lower on personal wherewithal than White participants. Indicating that the young Latinx participants in our study highly agreed with the belief in hard work ethic regardless of systemic or institutional issues that exist in our modern society.

These results contribute to the discussion of the growing number of Latinx identifying as Republicans, with Trump winning almost a third of the Latinx vote in 2016 (Reyes, 2020; Krogstad & Lopez, 2016). According to a CNN exit poll, in the 2020 presidential election, Donald Trump gained more Latinx voters in key battleground states than he won in 2016 (Agiesta et al., 2020). Even though the Trump Administration mishandled the pandemic, attempts to repeal the Affordable Care Act and restrict immigration (Abutaleb et al., 2020; Melillo, 2020; Norwood, 2020). According to Josh

Zaragoza, a Democratic data specialist in Arizona, most Latinx first identify as hard-working Americans, and Donald Trump speaks to that (Caputo, 2020). According to research conducted by the Pew Research Center, Latinx identity fades across generations as immigration connections are further away (Lopez et al., 2017). Thus, Latinx identity can be dissected and researched to understand how self-identity plays into political decisions such as voting in elections and political affiliation.

Limitations

This research, however, is subject to several limitations. In this investigation, the sample was relatively similar concerning age and education. Future research will be necessary to examine the current results of other communities, such as those living in extreme poverty or extreme wealth. As well as researching other age groups to see the generational differences towards immigrants and how that can influence an individual's ideology of the "American Dream." Another limitation is the lack of access to people who have crossed the U.S-Mexican border and examining their prosocial behavior towards people who have gone through the same, if not, similar experience. People crossing the border have a unique shared experience, and if this community was investigated, the results are subject to change. Lastly, our findings cannot be generalized beyond a Southwestern population that was mainly focused on recruiting college students from that state of California.

Table 1*Descriptive Statistics and Correlations for Study Variables*

Variables	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5
1. Political Position ^a	197	6.05	1.69	—				
2. Right-Wing Authoritarianism	197	3.17	0.94	.66**	—			
3. Social Dominance Orientation	197	2.45	1.21	.59**	.56**	—		
4. Personal Wherewithal	197	3.69	1.73	.70**	.64**	.62**	—	
5. Color-Blind Racism	197	2.96	1.44	.77**	.65**	.71**	.81**	—

Note. The results for the participants ($n=197$) are shown above.

^a1 = Extremely Liberal, 2 = Liberal, 3 = Slightly Liberal, 4 = Middle of Road Moderate, 5 = Slightly Conservative, 6 = Conservative, 7 = Extremely Conservative.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$ (two-tailed).

Table 2

Summary of Hierarchical Regression for Variables Predicting Political Positionality Among Participants

Variable	<i>B</i>	95% CI for <i>B</i>		<i>SE B</i>	β	<i>R</i> ²	ΔR^2
		<i>LL</i>	<i>UL</i>				
Step 1						.44	.43***
Constant	2.31***	1.68	2.94	0.32			
Right Wing Authoritarianism	1.18***	0.99	1.37	0.10	0.66***		
Step 2						.51	.51***
Constant	2.22***	1.63	2.81	0.30			
Right Wing Authoritarianism	0.85***	0.64	1.07	0.11	0.48***		
Social Dominance Orientation	0.46**	0.29	0.63	0.08	0.33**		
Step 3						.58	.57***
Constant	2.27***	1.73	2.82	0.28			
Right Wing Authoritarianism	0.56***	0.34	0.78	0.11	0.31***		
Social Dominance Orientation	0.26**	0.09	0.43	0.09	0.19**		
Personal Wherewithal	0.37***	0.24	0.50	0.07	0.38***		
Step 4						.65	.64***
Constant	2.40***	1.89	2.90	0.25			
Right Wing Authoritarianism	0.44***	0.23	0.65	0.11	0.25***		
Social Dominance Orientation	0.04	-0.13	0.21	0.09	0.03		
Personal Wherewithal	0.11	-0.04	0.26	0.07	0.11		
Color Blind Racism	0.59***	0.40	0.79	0.10	0.50***		

Note. CI = confidence interval; *LL* = lower limit; *UL* = upper limit

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$

Figure 1

Interaction Effect Between Ethnicity and Conditions on Personal Wherewithal

Note. This figure demonstrates the elements of a significant interaction effect.

Figure 2

Main Effect Between of Ethnicity on Institutional Discrimination

Note. This figure demonstrates the elements of a significant main effect.

Appendix A

NEWS CLIP #1

Please read the following narrative from a local Texas radio station reporting on families attempting to cross the border.

Rosa, 25, is the mother of an infant, Mateo, and lives in Ciudad Juarez, Mexico. For the past 7 years, she has been trying to immigrate to America due to the intense gang violence and fears she has in her city. She is a single mother because her husband was murdered by gang members. Last year, she pleaded for asylum in the United States for the safety of herself and her child, but was sent back to wait for an immigration court hearing. Recently, her body and her infant's body were found in a local river by the border of Texas with bullet wounds found in both mother and child. She had likely been shot down by border patrol attempting to cross the border.

Appendix B

NEWS CLIP #2

Below contains an excerpt from an article reported by CNN and published by the Texas Tribune. We've also included a link to the full story, if you wish to learn more, at your own discretion.

"A Honduran mother and her 21-month-old son died near Del Rio earlier this month after trying to cross the Rio Grande into Texas, a U.S. Customs and Border Protection spokesperson confirmed Friday. According to CNN, Idalia Yamileth Herrera Hernandez had recently crossed the U.S.-Mexico border with her son, Iker Gael Cordova Herrera, and requested asylum. But under the Trump administration's "remain in Mexico" program, they were sent back to Matamoros, Mexico, to wait for an immigration court hearing. They grew more and more desperate while waiting for their hearing and died while it was still pending, CNN reported.

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